

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BOUDALIA****FIRST NAME: MOHAMED EL AMIR****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)
The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 11 %

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-A401D

1. Two students discuss a specific point related to your domain of specialization. One of them gives his opinion on an original text he read, and the second shares an opinion reddened in Wikipedia about this original text. Which categories can describe these two sources?
- Both of the original text and the Wikipedia article are primary sources of evidence.
 - The original text is a primary source, and the Wikipedia article is a secondary source.
 - The original text is a primary source, and the Wikipedia article is a Tertiary source.¹**
 - The original text is a primary source, and the Wikipedia article is not a source.

¹ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 35–39.

2. All these situations describe Plagiarism except one, which one is wrong?
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses sources of information without citing the author of the source.
 - Plagiarism is when the writer takes someone's words or ideas without citing the original author.
 - Plagiarism is when the writer paraphrases a source without citing the original author.
 - Plagiarism is when the writer quotes an author explicitly.²**
3. A style guide can be useful in many ways. Which one of these sentences does not describe a style guide's aim?
- A style guide may provide rules for text formatting (font type and style, citation format).
 - A style guide is generally associated with a type of writing (journalism, governmental institution, academic or business writing).
 - The principal goal of a style guide is to ensure consistent writing.
 - A style guide describes which kinds of sources are allowed in a text.³**

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1.*, Fourth ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

³ *Ibid.*, 41.

4. Zotero is very useful in managing a long list of sources. Which sentences describe its function properly?
- Zotero is the only program available to manage source citations on a computer.
 - Microsoft word can't manage citation sources and references by itself, so Zotero is mandatory in essay redaction.
 - Zotero never makes any mistakes cause it's a computer program. There is no need to check the data collected by Zotero online.
 - Zotero can manage many style guide for citation but need the user to specify which one he wants to be used.**⁴
5. What is an Annotated bibliography?
- A bibliography that does not include all works cited in notes.
 - A separate list in addition to a standard bibliography.
 - A bibliography with a brief description of the work's contents.**⁵
 - A bibliography that provides a web link for all cited source.
6. Positivism is described as an empirical method. Which situation describes a positivist approach in those sentences?
- Laws or theories (deductive approach) govern the world, and these can be tested and verified (objective interpretation).**⁶

⁴ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers*, 145.

⁵ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers*, 155.

⁶ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers*, 149.

- Legacy Inherited from our ancestors explains everything (inductive approach). Every new observation should comply with the community's point of view (Subjective interpretation).
 - No knowledge can be derived from direct observation and logical inferences because it is always a subjective approach.
 - Positivism imply to systematically find a positive correlation between the experiment and the hypothesis.
7. If for performing your research study, you decide to use a methodology that leads to the inductive generation of theories that emerge from the data them self, you can describe this method as being based on the following:
- Grounded Theory approach.**⁷
 - Phenomenology approach.
 - Narrative inquiry approach.
 - Inductive approach.
8. Which sentence is wrong:
- The phenomenology method aims to understand what humans have in common in the way they experiment the world, assuming that there is some commonality in human experience and seeking to understand this commonality.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, Fourth edition. (Los Angeles London New Delhi Singapore Washington, DC Melbourne: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018), 251.

- Ethnography studies collectivistic experiences within a certain culture. This involves understanding their attitudes, beliefs, and behaviours on long-term observations.
 - Phenomenology may be conceived as a philosophy.
 - The purpose of phenomenological research is to investigate the impact of personal experience on collectivistic behavior.^{8,9}**
9. In qualitative analysis, there are three main ways of reasoning to solve a question; which sentences reflect an abductive analysis approach?
- Data lead to theory. Then, the researcher should "collect" data and "listen" to what data can provide as a general concept.
 - Theory leads to data. Then, the researcher will get a theory that leads to testing a hypothesis by determining the needed data to collect.
 - Situation leads to inquiry. The researcher makes an assumption that a connection exists in an incomplete or seemingly unrelated set of data.¹⁰**
 - Feeling leads to theory. The researcher makes a theory based on his immediate feeling.
10. Approval from The Institutional Review Board (IRB) is mandatory to start any study or research protocol that involves human beings as subjects of study. Which one of these prerogatives of the IRB is false:

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 168.

⁹ Hasa, "Difference Between Ethnography and Phenomenology | Definition, Features, Focus, Data Collection," *Pediaa.Com*, last modified February 14, 2017, accessed January 30, 2023, <https://pediaa.com/difference-between-ethnography-and-phenomenology/>.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 538.

- The IRB should ensure the compliance of the submitted study project with federal laws regarding protecting human subjects from harm.
- The necessity of protecting the dignity and personal and/or professional safety of research participants is one of the major aims of the IRB
- IRB approval requires that informed consent from all research participants be submitted before the beginning of the study.¹¹**
- IRBs are responsible for regulating, governance, and enforcing research ethics.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles London New Delhi Singapore Washington, DC Melbourne: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Hasa. "Difference Between Ethnography and Phenomenology | Definition, Features, Focus, Data Collection." *Pediaa.Com*. Last modified February 14, 2017. Accessed January 30, 2023. <https://pediaa.com/difference-between-ethnography-and-phenomenology/>.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago ; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

¹¹ L Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 226.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.